

The Current State of Improving the Methodological Preparation of Future Primary School Teachers for Teaching Technology

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Abstract:

This article is about classroom learning technologies, classroom learning technologies, learning materials, learning integrations, and learning integrations.

Keywords: technology, integration, integrated lesson, modern lesson, modern teacher, modern student, modern method.

The growth of scientific and technical development in the conditions of market relations requires the intellectual and creative content of the work of the future primary school teacher. This situation affects two main components of the educational process. These are: goals and tasks of education and organizational forms, methods and tools. The implementation of this algorithm is directly related to ensuring the continuity of education. The solution to the problem of continuity should be focused on ensuring the continuity of the components of general secondary education, secondary special education, vocational education and higher education.

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Pedagogical principles of developing students' technical creativity in the process of preparing them for work. , U.N. Nishonaliyev, B.S. Gafforov, V.P. Budarkevich, etc.

The initial and final stages of general secondary education determine the minimum level of

knowledge, skills and qualifications that students should acquire. It is clear that the state educational standard of general secondary education also includes the state educational standards of primary education and each academic subject. In particular, the educational subject of technology education is included in the "Man and Society" field of education in the state education standards of primary education, and in the 5-9th grades it is included in the science of technology.

The purpose of technology education in elementary grades is to introduce simple types of work, work process and simple types of work tools, to learn to perform simple work methods correctly, to plan them, to maintain workplace order, to safety rules. is to form qualities such as compliance. In the 5th-9th grades, general labor skills and competencies are developed in students. According to their interests and abilities, their professional inclinations, services aimed at choosing a voluntary and compulsory education, general work culture are formed and developed. Pupils are given the opportunity to get acquainted with various fields of labor activity, they are taught the technologies of production of consumer products.

Technology education in general secondary schools is the basis of preparation for the choice of a professional field of secondary special, vocational education, and its content mainly includes the following areas includes:

- 1) a special type of lesson that combines the teaching of several subjects at the same time in the study of concepts, topics or events. In such a lesson, auxiliary subjects are distinguished that serve to deepen, expand and clarify the material of the leading subject, which acts as an integrator;
- 2) the integrated lesson allows to separate the study of its subject from the traditional approach of education and bring education into a natural organic connection with the child's life.

In the organization of education and cognitive activity, creative and effective tasks that determine the meaning of innovative teaching are brought forward. The student's motives for choosing reproductive tasks correspond to the logic of increasing creativity, social significance and cultural usefulness of the result. This leads to self-organization of the system of cognitive activity, striving for new goals, changes in semantic relations. It also expands the zone of long-term development in students. In innovative teaching, goals and tasks are developed together with the teacher and students. The process of achieving them is organized as a joint activity. One of the priority directions in cooperative pedagogy is the set of integrated technologies, that is, the integrated lesson is one of the means of developing the cognitive activity of students and instilling it into their minds.

They make it possible to move from separate consideration of different phenomena in reality to complex interrelated studies. Integrated education makes it possible to identify the student's interests in a short period of time and determine the ways of their development, to improve the natural inclination of the individual. The following conditions are taken into account when planning and organizing such classes:

- a) the subject of analysis in the integrated content is multifaceted objects, information about their essence is found in the cross-section of different disciplines;
- b) in the formation of basic concepts, there is an opportunity to combine them, since the topic being studied is directly connected with the content of other academic subjects;
- c) subject and inter-subject relations can act simultaneously in the subject being studied.

For this, it is necessary to plan the educational material in such a way that the students fully and comprehensively perceive this or that new concept or event. It can be said that intersubject communication is a condition for improving the quality of the modern educational process, combining science and practice, integrating a person into national and world culture, the ability to establish scientific communication, and an indicator of the teacher's pedagogical skills.

An integrated lesson combines knowledge from different subjects, which is important for correctly

determining the main goal. If a common goal is defined, only the necessary aspects for its implementation are taken from the composition of objects. Planning requires a careful selection of the type and structure of the lesson, teaching methods and tools, as well as determining the optimal load of various types of student activity in the auditorium.

Integrated lessons are a source of finding new connections between different facts, which, in turn, confirm or deepen certain conclusions. A comprehensive lesson requires thorough preparation, professional skills and a culture of personal communication from the teacher. If the teacher's skills and enthusiasm are revealed in the lessons of this content, it will give more results. Integrated lessons may have different educational technologies, but they are modeled in the way of independent search for new optimal scheme-models, manifestation of the teacher's creative activity. So, modern civilization cannot be imagined without integration.

An integrated approach harmoniously combines various teaching methods - lecture, conversation, explanation, observation, analysis, comparison. "Modern lesson - modern teacher - modern student" refers to modern methods, methods and technologies. The speed and scope of today's information flow does not allow to tell everything, perform all tasks, and pass new materials within one lesson.

One of the most popular and new forms of modern teaching is the integrated lesson. Just reading about such a class, it is impossible not to imagine all the possibilities of such classes. But when integrated lessons are put into practice, it becomes clear that it penetrates the curriculum and connects disciplines that are not compatible with each other.

Experiments have shown that combined tasks and lessons are interesting not only for preschool, school (primary, middle and high school students) and higher education system. Different layers of materials in one lesson allow to make the lesson more interesting and meaningful at the same time. Diversification of students' activities allows them to be emotionally involved in solving the tasks set before them.

Teaching subjects of technological science in connection with visual arts. Technology as a scientific discipline is so versatile that it can be combined with almost any discipline. For example, it is closely related to mathematics, chemistry, physics, economics, etc., which makes it possible to implement both basic and prospective interdisciplinary communication.

The requirements of the era of globalization require the formation of a creative and active person with the ability to effectively and non-standardly solve social and economic changes in society, new life problems. Naturally, time will require rebuilding everything that does not meet the requirements of the upgrade process. This process is directly aimed at the development of the student's spirituality and thinking. must be read.

In recent years, due to the increased attention to the subjects of the aesthetic cycle, the problem of introducing effective methods of developing the artistic and creative abilities of a person into the educational process is gaining urgent importance. In our opinion, the possibilities of integrated education with the help of combined educational tools are wide. A comprehensive approach to the teaching of aesthetic cycle subjects is aimed at solving the problem of comprehensive development of the individual.

It is important to take into account the age characteristics and abilities of students in lessons that integrate technology and visual arts. Creative activity requires a person's passion, determination, strength and the ability to concentrate. Of course, the age of the student affects this process. His ability to plan work depends on the accuracy of hand movements, artistic and technical problems that develop coordination with the organs of sight, hearing and other senses. Also, a high sensitivity to the shape, size, color, composition and structure of the material becomes a condition for the development of abilities.

Skills are a person's ability to acquire more knowledge and skills. It is true that people have

different abilities. This is an important aspect, especially in the assessment of abilities, for an individual approach to teaching and training. Many abilities are "specialized," meaning they have a specific focus. The composition of capabilities includes characteristics for different purposes, some of which are leading, others are supporting, and some form a certain background necessary for effective functioning. The structure of abilities is very flexible, the composition of components can change, which leads to their reconstruction.

The leading feature of creative activity is a person's developed aesthetic attitude towards reality, aesthetic tools related to emotional perception. Students have different levels of intelligence and creativity. It is known that creativity cannot be taught by being limited to a show, film or story. This requires proper organization of student activities.

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